

South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA): Spider diversity of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Gauteng province, South Africa

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Abstract: The first checklist of the spider species of Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve in Gauteng, South Africa, is presented. Spiders were collected over a period of 10 years, and 37 families, represented by 113 genera and 142 species, are listed. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (24 spp.), followed by the Thomisidae (15 spp.), Gnaphosidae (14 spp.) and Araneidae (13 spp.), while 18 families are singletons. Information on the endemism and conservation status of each species is provided as well as a photo gallery of some species. Approximately 6% of the total South African spider fauna are protected in the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve.

Key words: endemism, conservation status, photo gallery

INTRODUCTION

Gauteng is one of the nine provinces of South Africa and covers an area of approximately 17 800 km², accounting for only 1.5% of the South African land area. It was previously known as part of the Transvaal province until South Africa's first democratic elections on 27 April 1994. The province falls within both the Savanna and highly threatened Grassland biomes and approximately 83% of the province falls within Highveld Grassland vegetation types, of which a mere 0.8% is currently conserved in South Africa (Pfab, 2001).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) that was initiated in 1997 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), extensive sampling took place in the Gauteng province. Presently, 561 species are known from this small province but only a few papers have yet been published on spider surveys of the province (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Lyle, 2014). These include surveys at the Roodeplaat Research Station (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1976), Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1989), Rietondale Research Station (Van den Berg & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991), and Faerie Glenn Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022).

The aim of this study is to provide a first checklist of the spider fauna of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (SRNR), near Heidelberg in Gauteng. The annotated checklist is accompanied by levels of endemism and conservation status data on each species.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The SRNR (-25.8, 28.77) is located about an hour's drive from Oliver Tambo International Airport and near the town of Heidelberg, in Gauteng. The reserve (134 km²) is situated in the Suikerbosrand Range in the rocky Highveld Grassland Biome (Figs 1–3). The altitude varies between 1 545 and 1 917 m above sea level.

The Suikerbosrand ridge was originally named after a sweet reed found growing here in 1836. Later the ridge and consequently the reserve's name became associated with the characteristic Transvaal sugarbush (*Protea caffra*), a dominant vegetation type within the reserve. The reserve falls within the summer rainfall area, with hot summers and cold winters with frost. Hail is common during summer thunderstorms. Maximum temperatures in midwinter average 19 °C and the minimum average is 5 °C. Midsummer maximum temperatures average 28 °C and the minimum average is 17 °C.

Figs 1–3. Some of the the habitat types in the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve. Photos: Johan van Zyl.

Fig. 3. Study area Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve, Gauteng.

Fig. 4. Entrance to the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve.

Study period and methods: Spiders were collected over a period of several years from 2009 to 2020 using different collecting methods to sample both the ground and field layers. The surveys were undertaken by:

- Members of the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council.
- Students of the North-West University during their annual survey activities in 2009–2010.
- Members of the Gauteng Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (GDARD) then known as Gauteng Department of Agriculture and Rural Development (GDACE) as part of their Gauteng Biodiversity GAP Analysis Project (Pfab, 2001).
- The second author lives next to the reserve and he regularly photographed spiders from the reserve.

Identification, photography and voucher specimens: Identifications were done in Pretoria by the first author (ASD) and the voucher specimens are housed in the NCA at the Agricultural Research Council-Plant Health and Protection division in Pretoria. Some of the species could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved (Tables 1 & 3). The photographs were donated to the SANSA Virtual Museum (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

Endemicity: The endemicity values for each species were determined (Table 3) based on their currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised:

- 6 = when SRNR is the type locality.
- 5 = GE, endemic to the Gauteng province but wider than the type locality.
- 4 = SAE, endemic to South Africa but known from only two adjoining provinces.
- 3 = SAE, South African endemic, known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining.
- 2 = STHE, endemic to Southern Africa (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers).
- 1 = AE, known from the Afrotropical Region (African Endemic).
- 0 = cosmopolitan, Africa and wider.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of least concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 142 species from 37 families and 113 genera are presently known from SRNR. Three species (Sparassidae and Zodariidae) could not be identified to species level as they were still immature.

Family diversity: Of the 37 spider families collected from SRNR (Tables 1 & 3), the Salticidae with 24 species is the most diverse family, followed by Thomisidae (15 spp.), Gnaphosidae (14 spp.), and Araneidae (13 spp.) (Table 1). Eighteen species are known from only a single species.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve listing the total number of families, genera (G), and species (SPP.)

FAMILIES	G	SPP.	FAMILIES	G	SPP.
Agelenidae	2	2	Philodromidae	4	6
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Pholcidae	2	2
Araneidae	11	13	Phyxelididae	2	2
Bemmeridae	1	1	Pisauridae	4	4
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	Prodidomidae	1	1
Clubionidae	1	1	Salticidae	17	24
Corinnidae	2	2	Scytodidae	1	1
Cyrtacheniidae	1	2	Segestriidae	1	1
Deinopidae	1	1	Selenopidae	1	1
Eresidae	1	2	Sparassidae	2	2
Gnaphosidae	10	14	Tetragnathidae	1	1
Hahniidae	1	1	Theraphosidae	1	1
Idiopidae	1	1	Theridiidae	7	7
Linyphiidae	2	2	Thomisidae	9	15
Liocranidae	1	1	Trachelidae	1	1
Lycosidae	9	14	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Oecobiidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Oxyopidae	3	3	Zodariidae	5	6
Palpimanidae	1	1	37 families	113	142

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species recorded from the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve

Conservation status	No. spp.	Code	%
Data deficient (taxonomic reason or lack distribution data)	0	DD	0
Not evaluated (immature, new or undetermined)	3	NE	2.1
Least concern	138	LC	97.9
Vulnerable	0	VU	0
Near threatened	0	NT	0
Endemism			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	17	LC	12.1
1 – African endemics (AE)	59	LC	41.8
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	30	LC	21.3
3 – South African endemics (SAE): More than three provinces	29	LC	20.6
4 – South African endemics (SAE): Two adjacent provinces	4	LC	2.8
5 – Gauteng endemics (GE)	0	VU,NT	0
6 – Type locality	0	0	0

Conservation status: The majority (97.9%) of species have a wide distribution and without known threats and are listed as Least Concern. The three species not evaluated were still immature. None of the species recorded are of special concern.

Endemism: Seventeen species (12.1%) sampled at SRNR have a wider distribution than Africa (C), while 41.8% are known from Africa (AE) and 21.3 % are known from Southern Africa and only 2.8% are South African endemics.

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Figs 5–20. 5–12: Araneidae: 5. *Caerostris sexcupidata*. 6. *Eriovixia excelsa*. 7. *Neoscona subfusca*. 8. *Cyphalonotus larvatus*. 9. *Neoscona moreli*. 10. *Trichonephila fenestrata*. 11. *Pararaneus cyrtoscapus*. 12. *Neoscona hirta*. 13. *Cheiracanthium furculatum* (Cheiracanthiidae). 14. *Clubiona pongolensis* (Clubionidae). 15. *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* (Cyrtaucheniidae). 16. *Menneus camelus* (Deinopidae). 17. *Setaphis subtilis* (Gnaphosidae). 18. *Microlinyphia sterilis* (Linyphiidae). 19. *Proevippa albiventris* (Lycosidae). 20. *Oecobius navus* (Oecobiidae). Photos: Johan van Zyl.

Figures 21–35. 21. *Hamataliwa kulczynskii* (Oxyopidae). 22. *Philodromus guineensis* (Philodromidae). 23. *Thanatus atlanticus* (Philodromidae). 24. *Rothus aethiopicus* (Pisauridae). 25. *Euprostenops australis* (Pisauridae). 26. *Baryphas ahenus* (Salticidae). 27. *Heliophanus transvaalicus* (Salticidae). 28. *Thyene natalii* (Salticidae). 29. *Heliophanus patellaris* (Salticidae). 30. *Tidarren cuneolatum* (Theridiidae). 31. *Runcinia aethiops* (Thomisidae). 32. *Simorcus cotti* (Thomisidae). 33. *Synema imitatrix* (Thomisidae). 34. *Thomisus citrinellus* (Thomisidae). 35. *Platyoides walteri* (Trochanteriidae). Photos: Johan van Zyl.

TABLE 3. Checklist of the spiders species recorded from the Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve in Gauteng with information on their endemicity (ENDV), conservation status (CON), country endemicity (CEND), and provincial endemics (PROVE). * possibly new species or new record.

FAMILY	SPECIES	ENDV	CON	CEND
1. Agelenidae	<i>Agelena gaerdesi</i> Roewer, 1955	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
2. Amaurobiidae	<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
3. Araneidae	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hypsosinga lithyphantoides</i> Caporiacco, 1947	1	LC	AE
	<i>Larinia bifida</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona hirta</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona moreli</i> (Vinson, 1863)	0	LC	C
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C
	<i>Pararaneus cyrtoscapus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pycnacantha tribulus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
	4. Bemmeridae	<i>Homostola vulpecula</i> Simon, 1892	3	LC
5. Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
6. Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona pongolensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
7. Corinnidae	<i>Cambalida fulvipes</i> Simon, 1896	1	LC	AE
	<i>Copa flavoplumosa</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE
8. Cyrtaucheniidae	<i>Ancylotrypa brevivalpis</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ancylotrypa nigriceps</i> (Purcell, 1902)	3	LC	SAE
9. Deinopidae	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
10. Eresidae	<i>Dresserus colsoni</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Dresserus kannemeyeri</i> Tucker, 1920	4	LC	SAE
11. Gnaphosidae	<i>Ammoxenus amphalodes</i> Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Asemesthes purcelli</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Camillina cordifera</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Drassodes stationis</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ibala arcus</i> (Tucker, 1923)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Ibala lapidaria</i> (Lawrence, 1928)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Marinarozelotes jaxartensis</i> (Kroneberg, 1875)	0	LC	C
	<i>Micaria beaufortia</i> Tucker, 1923	1	LC	AE
	<i>Setaphis subtilis</i> (Simon, 1897)	0	LC	C
	<i>Xerophaeus appendiculatus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes reduncus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes sclateri</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
12. Hahniidae	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
13. Idiopidae	<i>Ctenolophus fenoulheti</i> Hewitt, 1913	3	LC	SAE
14. Linyphiidae	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1879)	0	LC	C
15. Liocranidae	<i>Rhaeboctesis transvaalensis</i> Tucker, 1920	3	LC	SAE

TABLE 3 continue

16. Lycosidae	<i>Allocosa nebulosa</i> (Roewer, 1960)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Foveosa adunca</i> Russell-Smith, Alderweireldt & Jocqué, 2007	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Hippasa australis</i> Lawrence, 1927	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hippasa funerea</i> Lessert, 1925	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hogna lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1960)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Hogna spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna transvaalica</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa albiventris</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zenonina albocaudata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
17. Oecobiidae	<i>Oecobius navus</i> Blackwall, 1859	0	LC	C
18. Oxyopidae	<i>Hamataliwa kulczynskii</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes hoggi</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
19. Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus transvaalicus</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
20. Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus bigibbus australis</i> Lawrence, 1928	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE
	<i>Suemus punctatus</i> Lawrence, 1938	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thanatus atlanticus</i> Berland, 1936	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tibellus hollidayi</i> Lawrence, 1952	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
21. Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana hectori</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
22. Phyxelididae	<i>Pongolania chrysonaria</i> Griswold, 1990	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Vidole lyra</i> Griswold, 1990	3	LC	SAE
23. Pisauridae	<i>Cispus variegatus</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euprosthops australis</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
	<i>Euprosthopsis vuattouxi</i> Blandin, 1977	1	LC	AE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
24. Prodidomidae	<i>Theuma elucubata</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
25. Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Dendryphantes hararensis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Evarcha flagellaris</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	1	LC	AE
	<i>Festucula leroyae</i> Azarkina & Foord, 2014	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Harmochirus luculentus</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus aberdarensis</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus charlesi</i> Wesolowska, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Heliophanus patellaris</i> Simon, 1901	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus pistaciae</i> Wesolowska, 2003	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Mexcala elegans</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE

Table 3 continue

	<i>Magrus mathisi</i> (Berland & Millot, 1941)	0	LC	C
	<i>Myrmarachne uvira</i> Wanless, 1978	1	LC	AE
	<i>Natta horizontalis</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nigorella hirsuta</i> Wesolowska, 2009	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes bulawayoensis</i> Wesolowska, 2000	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	0	LC	C
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pignus simoni</i> (Peckham & Peckham, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene semiargentea</i> (Simon, 1884)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tusitala barbata</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	1	LC	AE
26. Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna corticola</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE
27. Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes fusca</i> Walckenaer, 1837	0	LC	C
28.. Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops barbertonensis</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Anyphops lawrencei</i> (Roewer, 1951)	2	LC	STHE
29. Sparassidae	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Parapalystes</i> sp. imm.			NE
30. Tetragnathidae	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
31. Theraphosidae	<i>Harpactira hamiltoni</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
30. Theridiidae	<i>Enoplognatha molesta</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C
	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer, 1847)	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Tidarren cuneolatum</i> (Tullgren, 1910)	1	LC	AE
31. Thomisidae	<i>Ansiae tuckeri</i> (Lessert, 1919)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses austrinus</i> Simon, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> Lucas, 1864	0	LC	C
	<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxytate argenteooculata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
	<i>Smodicinus coroniger</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus citrinellus</i> Simon, 1875	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Xysticus urbensis</i> Lawrence, 1952	2	LC	STHE
32. Trachelidae	<i>Afroceto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
33. Trochanteriidae	<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1886)	1	LC	AE
34. Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas, 1846	0	LC	C

Table 3 continue

35. Zodariidae	<i>Cydrela schoemanae</i> Jocqué, 1991	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Diores rectus</i> Jocqué, 1990	1	LC	AE
	<i>Diores recurvatus</i> Jocqué, 1990	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Microdiores</i> sp. *			NE
	<i>Ranops</i> sp. *			NE
	<i>Systemoplacis vandami</i> (Hewitt, 1916)	3	LC	SAE